

Strategies to mitigate ammonia emissions to the atmosphere from outdoor storage from livestock manure

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Abstract text

The outdoor storage of livestock manure is one of the main sources of ammonia (NH₃) emission into the atmosphere. Gaseous ammonia in the atmosphere leads to the formation of secondary inorganic aerosols, the main constituents of anthropogenic PM_{2.5} emissions. Fine particulate matter causes lung cancer and cardiopulmonary diseases and, indirectly, ammonia emissions also contribute to N₂O secondary emissions. Emissions from livestock effluents and livestock production in general are also related to greenhouse gases (GHGs), which include methane (CH₄), carbon dioxide (CO₂), and nitrous oxide (N₂O).

Several strategies can be implemented to mitigate the emissions to the atmosphere of outdoor storage of livestock manure, such as covering pits (Webb et al., 2005), using submerged bioelectrochemical systems to recover ammonium (Cerrillo et al., 2023) or acidifying slurry to avoid ammonium conversion into ammonia gas (Fangueiro et al., 2015).

The main aim of this study was to evaluate the effectiveness of acidification of pig slurry stored in an outdoor pit during the Mediterranean summer season, to ensure the suitability of this technique to hot climates. A pilot acidification plant was installed at the IRTA facilities in Caldes de Montbui. The pilot plant was composed of two 5 m³ pig slurry pits, the first acting as a control, while the second was equipped with a system to monitor pH value and acidify the slurry to a pH of 5.5 with sulphuric acid (H₂SO₄, 95 %). Pig slurry was collected from a sow farm in Caldes de Montbui (Barcelona, Spain), with the following characteristics: pH, 7.79±0.04; conductivity, 11.7±0.1 mS/cm; total solids, 0.73±0.03%; chemical oxygen demand, 4.3±0.4 g/L; total Kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN), 1.37±0.02 g/kg; ammonia nitrogen, 1.19±0.03 g/kg. The emission from the pits was monitored with a dynamic hood and an ammonia sensor for 80 days in the summer season, with an average ambient temperature of 26 °C, and a range between 13 °C and 41.6 °C.

The consumption of sulphuric acid to maintain the pig slurry at an average pH value of 5.5 was of 3.7 kg/m³. In 80 days, TKN in the control pit decreased by 64%, from 1.5 g/kg to 0.5 g/kg. In contrast, the acidified pig slurry pit had a TKN concentration of 2.0 g/kg at the end of the assay. Besides, the nitrogen emission rate of the control pit reached 1.15 g/m²/h at the beginning of the assay, while it decreased as the TKN decreased, up to a value of 0.03 g/m²/h (Figure 1). The acidified pit showed an emission

rate under the detection limit most of sampling times, achieving an average reduction of 97% compared to the control pit.

The acidification technique in outdoor storage pits with sow pig manure has shown, first of all, its usefulness for the conservation of the nitrogen content and its fertilizing power, while in the control pit 64% of the nitrogen was lost in 80 days. Secondly, in a period with extremely warm temperatures, the nitrogen emission rate in the acidified pond achieved an average emission reduction of 97%. The next trials will evaluate the effectiveness of this technique with slurry with a higher concentration of nitrogen, such as those obtained from pig fattening farms.

Figure 1. Nitrogen emission rate of the acidified pit and the control pit.

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